

SustAIIn Liv Work /

CENTRE OF
EXCELLENCE OF
ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE
FOR SUSTAINABLE
LIVING AND
WORKING

Co-funded by
the European Union

ADVANCING AI FOR SUSTAINABLE WORLD

WE'RE EXCITED ABOUT THE POSSIBILITIES OF SUSTAINABLE AI FUTURE

The project is co-funded under the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No. 101059903 and under the European Union Funds' Investments 2021–2027 (project No. 10-042-P-0001).

CONTENTS

ABOUT THE PROJECT	3
WHO WE ARE	5
OUR STRATEGIC FOCUS & MAIN ACTIVITIES	7
OUR IMPACT	10

SustAIN
Liv
Work

ABOUT THE PROJECT

Launched in 2023, the SustAIInLivWork Centre of Excellence (CoE) for Sustainable Living and Working was established to pioneer cutting-edge solutions powered by Artificial Intelligence (AI). The CoE focuses on driving innovation across four critical domains: industry, energy, transport, and health, addressing pressing challenges with sustainable, AI-driven advancements.

It will have an impact on the country, the wider Baltic Sea Region, and beyond through the operation of 4 hubs.

These hubs will lead to the development of new educational and training programmes, strengthened collaboration with the private sector and public authorities, and the establishment of a Lithuanian AI Cluster to drive the transition towards sustainability, with a particular focus on the S3 (Smart Specialisation strategy) priorities areas.

4 HUBS

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT HUB

AI RESEARCH HUB

GRANT DEVELOPMENT HUB

TECH-TRANSFER, IMPACT AND
KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION HUB

WHO WE ARE

SustAIInLivWork Centre of Excellence acts as a lighthouse with far reaching impact strengthening R&I in the national and international scope.

It is built on strategic collaboration between key national partners:

Lithuania's four leading universities –

- | Kaunas University of Technology (KTU),
- | Vytautas Magnus University (VMU),
- | Lithuanian University of Health Sciences (LSMU),
- | Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (VILNIUS TECH);

and advanced international ones –

- | Tampere University (Finland),
- | Hamburg University of Technology (Germany).

These partners contribute their expertise to enhance value creation through advanced AI technologies.

SELECTED AREAS OF EXPERTISE

kaunas
university of
technology

VYTAUTAS
MAGNUS
UNIVERSITY
M C M X X I I

TUHH
Hamburg
University of
Technology

**VILNIUS
TECH**
Vilnius Gediminas
Technical University

LITHUANIAN UNIVERSITY
OF HEALTH SCIENCES

Tampere
University

Prediction & Anomaly
Detection Systems

Planning and Optimisation
Algorithms

Big Data Analysis and
Processing

Development of
AI-Powered Software

(Bio)medical Image
Analysis

Sustainable Energy
Solutions

AI Software & Hardware
Commercialisation

Autonomous Mobile
Machines

Clinical Data
Analysis

Robotic System Design &
Development

Efficient Energy
Solution Development

CO₂-Neutral City
Solutions and Strategies

OUR VISION

To boost Lithuania's capabilities to develop AI solutions for sustainable living and working, developing and promoting the uptake of advanced AI technologies and sustainability strategies of advanced partners (TAU, TUHH) across Lithuania, Baltic Sea Region and beyond.

OUR STRATEGIC FOCUS

To establish and operate the CoE with a long-term vision, ensuring self-sustainability and fostering AI innovations.

To conduct cutting-edge research in sustainable AI and educate diverse stakeholders on its benefits.

To drive transformative change in AI solutions for sustainable living and working, serving society at large.

To create a Lithuanian AI cluster to foster transitions towards sustainability, with a particular focus on S3 priority areas.

MAIN ACTIVITIES OF THE CENTRE

AI LABORATORIES AND SYSTEMS

Intelligent systems modelling, business analytics, and sandbox environments with test-before-invest AI labs for external organisations.

PRACTICAL TRAINING AND EDUCATION

Value-added training programmes and courses that integrate best practices for implementing AI solutions while prioritising sustainability in the private and public sectors.

SYSTEMS DEVELOPMENT AND EVALUATION

AI solutions implementation, dual-environment testing, and certification for compliance and reliability.

DATA ANALYSIS

Customised data storage and computing infrastructure with 3A data services: analysis, annotation, and anonymisation for AI applications.

NEW GENERATION INTELLIGENT SOLUTIONS

Personalised Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) solutions providing higher levels of understanding while maintaining human oversight of AI systems.

PATENTS

New patents focused on delivering ethical, sustainable, robust, and high-quality intelligent technology performance.

KEY SECTORS

MANUFACTURING

ENERGY

HEALTH

TRANSPORT

BENEFITS FOR BUSINESS

- | HIGH-VALUE, PERSONALISED TRAINING
- | ACCESS TO FACILITIES AND EQUIPMENT
- | POOL OF INNOVATIVE IDEAS
- | INFLUENCE RESEARCH DIRECTION
- | RISK-FREE AI TRIALS
- | EXPANDED R&D CAPACITY

OUR IMPACT

ACADEMIC LEADERSHIP

Stronger collaboration among leading research institutions to boost international achievements and foster synergies with EU partners in projects.

SYNERGY BETWEEN BUSINESS AND THE PUBLIC SECTOR

Driving institutional and systemic reforms, encouraging investment in R&D&I (Research and Development and Innovation), and building a modern, competitive Lithuanian R&D ecosystem.

Strengthening the role of higher education in developing frontier research and integrating innovative solutions across Lithuania's R&D ecosystem, while aiming for leadership in programmes such as Horizon Europe.

COLLABORATION

The Centre as a role model for improving Lithuania's R&D culture to develop and promote interdisciplinary, ethical, sustainable research in AI by strengthening connections between academia, business and the public sector.

R&D&I MODERNISATION

GET IN TOUCH

 A. Baršausko St. 59-449, Kaunas, Lithuania

 agne.paulauskaite-taraseviciene@ktu.lt

PARTNER WITH US

to drive AI innovations that transform sustainability across Lithuania and beyond!